

hip-TNBC grant (Izp-2023/1-0020)

Version 0

Description

DMP for hipTNBC is created to track all the result documentation created in this project.

Aim of the project: to identify and to verify molecular alterations, and clinically actionable targets associated with continuous acute, chronic, prolonged, and intermittent (cycling) hypoxia in triple negative breast cancer reference cell lines (TNBC-RCL) to advance the development of personalized therapy for breast cancer (BC) patients. Also, the proposed study plans to explore the effects of various modes of hypoxia on the transcriptomic and proteomic expression status of hypoxia-inducible factors (HIFs), as well as mitochondrial apoptotic priming system in TNBC-RCL.

Scientific Objectives (SO):

1. SO1: To perform bioinformatics analysis in publicly available TNBC multi-omics data sets (TCGA, METABRIC) for identification of novel acute continuous and cycling hypoxia-associated molecular alterations (potential biomarkers) and relevant druggable targets.
2. SO2: To verify molecular alterations identified in bioinformatics analysis, as well as 15-gene expression continuous acute hypoxia signature¹⁴ and cycling hypoxia signature²⁰ in the panel of TNBC-RCLs exposed to various modes of hypoxia.
3. SO3: To explore the transcriptomic and proteomic expression status of various isoforms of HIFs (HIF-1, HIF- 2, HIF-3) during exposure of TNBC-RCLs to various modes of hypoxia.

4. SO4: To identify mitochondrial apoptotic dependencies²¹ induced by various hypoxia conditions for identification of druggable targets for BH3 mimetics.

5. SO5: To explore the effects of various modes of hypoxia on the sensitivity of TNBC-RCLs to the pharmacological agents identified in the bioinformatics and mitochondrial apoptotic priming dependency analysis.

WP1: Bioinformatics analysis of publicly available data sets to identify hypoxia-induced molecular alterations specific to TNBC. - responsible: V.Pirsko

WP2: Culture of TNBC-RCLs across various modes of hypoxia to obtain samples for hypoxia associated feature analysis. - responsible: I.Mitre

WP3: Analysis of hypoxia-specific gDNA, mRNA, miRNA, and protein features in hypoxic TNBC-RCLs. - responsible: I.Cakstina-Dzerve/O.Rogoza

WP4: Analysis of the mitochondrial apoptotic priming dependencies in hypoxic TNBC-RCLs. - responsible: I.Cakstina-Dzerve/O.Rogoza

WP5: The effects of hypoxia on sensitivity of TNBC-RCLs to pharmacological agents identified in WP1 and WP4. - responsible: I.Cakstina-Dzerve/O.Rogoza

WP6. Preparation of manuscripts for publications.- responsible: I.Cakstina-Dzerve/O.Rogoza/V.Pirsko/I.Mitre

Funder

Latvijas Zinātnes padome

Grant

hip-TNBC grant (Izp-2023/1-0020)

Researchers

Olesja Rogoza (orcid:0000-0003-2161-0433), Valdis Pirsko
(orcid:0000-0002-9354-663X)

Organizations

Riga Stradiņš University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [hip-TNBC grant \(Izp-2023/1-0020\)](#)

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Researchers:

[Olesja Rogoza \(orcid:0000-0003-2161-0433\)](#)

[Valdis Pirsko \(orcid:0000-0002-9354-663X\)](#)

Organizations:

[Riga Stradiņš University](#)

Contact: [Inese Cakstina-Dzerve](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvijas Zinātnes padome

Grants: hip-TNBC grant (Izp-2023/1-0020)

Project: BDFSR

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Tabular data of experiments

All the data consisting of numerical values (e.g. cell viability data).

Template: RSU DMP Template

Type: Dataset

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To gather all the raw and analysed data of the project needed for reports and publications.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

lab personell, students, other researchers

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

ATCC catalogue : <https://www.atcc.org/cell-products>

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

- codebook
- laboratory notebooks and experimental protocols
- methodology description

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

File naming is based on several approaches, but they always will include the file creators initials (ICD - Inese Cakstina-Dzerve, VP - Valdis Pirsko, IM - Ingrida Mitre, OR - Olesja Rogoza) and dates (by the dates one can follow up in person's notebook).

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Mostly data will be as xcl or csv files.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

CSV is a widely accessible file format with different software tools, including open source ones

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Access will be granted upon a concrete proposal on the potential scientific collaboration, as well as stating the purpose for re-using this dataset.

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

No

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2025-12-31

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- storage
- archiving
- processing

Euro

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data?

Riga Stradinš University (RSU)

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Inese Cakstina-Dzerve (orcid:0000-0001-5589-0395)

3.1.5 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Crosscheck by the team members, as well as a quality check upon depositing the data.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research?

RSU Share-point

3.2.4 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

RSU Dataverse has all the necessary measures to ensure secure long term preservation and curation.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data?

No

3.3.5 Will data collected/generated include sensitive information?

No

Fluorescence and bright field microscopy image data

Fluorescent and bright field microscopy images of successful experiments, needed for reports, dissemination and publications.

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To have visualizations of successful IF and other experiments involving microscopy.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

lab personell, students, other researchers

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- pdf
- tiff

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

1 TB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

- codebook
- laboratory notebooks and experimental protocols
- methodology description
- software documentation

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

It will be mostly TIFF data, however for analysis, one will need specific programme.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

For tiff files - any imaging software, for analysis files - InCell Developer, Cell Profiler

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?
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- storage
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- security
- processing

Euro

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3.1.5 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Crosscheck by team members, as well as quality check upon deposition of the data

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

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3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research?

RSU Share-point (another back-up will be the external hard drive).

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No

Textual data describing experimental design and result interpretations

Personell notebooks, publication drafts, meeting notes etc.

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To follow-up of the data and experiments and decisions during the project (meeting notes). To access the detailed information of numerical and image data.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

lab personell, students, researchers

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

- Programme source code
- Experimental data
- Textual data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- txt
- pdf
- csv
- others

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

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2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

- codebook
- readme file
- laboratory notebooks and experimental protocols
- methodology description

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Yes

PDV, CSV, TXT are widely accessible file formats

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

PDV, CSV, TXT are widely accessible file formats

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2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

No

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2025-02-10

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

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